

GEOLOGICAL POSITION AND MINERAL COMPOSITION OF THE LOWEST MINED LEVELS OF THE KASHANA BARITE DEPOSIT (PRELIMINARY DATA)

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ABSTRACT. The Kashana Deposit is located in the northern part of the Srednogorie magmatic and metallogenic zone, in the Elatzite–Chelopech ore field, between the town of Etropole and the village of Chelopech, near the Elatzite Cu-porphry deposit and the Chelopech Au-Cu epithermal deposit. The mineralisation of the Kashana barite deposit is related to the Late Cretaceous intermediate Ca-alkaline magmatism. It was discovered in 1929 and its underground operation started in 1939. The aim of the present study is to determine the mineral composition of samples from the lowest mined part of the deposit using optical microscopy, XRD, and SEM methods of investigation. The deposit is hydrothermal, vein type. The main mineral is barite, but the current study establishes the presence of minor minerals, like quartz, muscovite, and hematite. The barite raw material is characterised by massive texture, high whiteness, and low content of Sr.

Key words: barite, mineral composition, mineral deposit, critical raw materials.

ГЕОЛОЖКО ПОЛОЖЕНИЕ И МИНЕРАЛЕН СЪСТАВ НА НАЙ-НИСКИТЕ ЕКСПЛОАТАЦИОННИ ХОРИЗОНТИ НА БАРИТНОТО НАХОДИЩЕ „КАШАНА“ (ПРЕДВАРИТЕЛНИ ДАННИ)

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РЕЗЮМЕ. Находище „Кашана“ се намира в северната част на Средногорската магмена и металогенна зона. То попада в Елашко-Челопешкото рудно поле, между град Етрополе и Челопеч, в близост до които се намират медно-порфирното находище „Елаците“ и медно-златно-епитермалното находище „Челопеч“. Минерализацията на баритното находище „Кашана“ е свързана с къснокредия калциево-алкален магматизъм, проявен в района. То е открито през 1929 година, а неговото подземно разработване започва през 1939 година. Целта на настоящото изследване е определянето на минералния състав на проби от най-ниските разработвани нива на находището. Използвани са оптична микроскопия, рентгено-структурен анализ и сканираща-електронна микроскопия. Находището е хидротермално от жилнен тип. Най-широко разпространеният минерал е барита. При настоящото изследване е установено е присъствието в малки количества на: кварц, мусковит и хематит. Баритната суровина се характеризира с масивна текстура, висока белиота и ниско съдържание на стронций.

Ключови думи: барит, минерален състав, баритно находище, суровини от критично значение.

Introduction

Barite is naturally occurring $BaSO_4$. Barium can be substituted isomorphously by Sr and Ca. Barite is inert and non-toxic. It has high density (4.5 g/cm^3), low hardness 2.5-3.5 (on the Moss scale), and low oil absorption. It is part of the list of critical raw materials according to the European Commission (European Commission, Study on the EU's list of Critical Raw Materials, 2020). About 60% of barite consumption is for weighting agent in oil and gas drilling fluids, about 30% for fillers in rubbers, plastic, paints, and paper production, and about 10% in the chemical industry. The leading world suppliers of barite are China (about 40% of the world production), followed by India and Morocco. In the EU, the only mining activities are in Germany (primary) and Bulgaria (reworking tailings) (European Commission, Study on the EU's list of Critical Raw Materials, 2020).

The biggest part of extracted barite in Bulgaria in the second half of the 20th century came from the Stara Zagora (open pit) and the Kashana (underground) deposits and later from Kremikovtsi (open pit) mine. The largest part of mined barite in Bulgaria was exported. More than 75 barite deposits were in operation in Bulgaria during the previous century (Andreevich, et. al. 1989).

The aim of our investigation is to determine the mineral composition of the barite raw material from the lowest levels of underground extraction in the Kashana mine.

Geology of the Kashana deposit

The Kashana deposit is situated in the northern part of the Central Srednogorie volcano-plutonic area, which forms part of the Srednogorie tectonic and magmatic and metallogenic zone (Dabovski et al., 2002), (Fig. 1). The deposit is situated in the Elatzite – Chelopech ore field, between the town of Etropole and the village of Chelopech, near the Elatzite Cu-porphry deposit and the Chelopech Au-Cu epithermal deposit.

Fig. 1. Tectonic Scheme of Bulgaria (after Dabovski et al., 2002) with the location of the Elatzite, Chelopech and Kashana deposits

The mineralisation of the Kashana barite deposit is related to the Late Cretaceous intermediate Ca-alkaline magmatism. The basement in the area consists of high-grade metamorphic

rocks (two-mica migmatites with thin intercalations of amphibolites, amphibole-biotite, and biotite gneisses) of Pirdop Group (Dabovski, 1988), and low metamorphic phyllites and diabases of the Berkovitsa group (Early Paleozoic island-arc volcanic complex) (Haydoutov, 2001), (Fig. 2). These units are in tectonic contact with each other, and to the north of Chelopech the phyllites of the Berkovitsa group are intruded by the Variscan granitoids (Kamenov et al., 2002) of the Vezhen pluton – hornblende-biotite granodiorite and granite of Carboiferous age. The Late Cretaceous succession in the region is presented by magmatic and sedimentary rocks. In the area of the Elatzite Cu-porphyry deposit, the Upper Cretaceous magmatism is represented by 3 units: 1 – subvolcanic quartz-monzonite porphyrites, 2 – granodiorite porphyrites, and 3 – aplites (Kamenov et al., 2003). The Late Cretaceous sedimentary succession in the southern part of region starts with conglomerates and coarse-grained sandstones intercalated with coal-bearing interbeds (coal-bearing formation) (Moev and Antonov, 1978) covered by polymictic, argillaceous and arkose sandstones to siltstones (sandstone formation). Pollen data suggests that both formations are Turonian (Stoykov and Pavlishina, 2003). The sedimentary rocks are cut by volcanic bodies and overlain by sedimentary and volcanic rocks of the Chelopech Formation (Moev and Antonov, 1978). It comprises the products of the Chelopech volcanic complex, epiclastics, as well as the Vozdol sandstones. The latter are paleontologically dated as Turonian in age (Stoykov and Pavlishina, 2003). These formations have been eroded and transgressively covered by sedimentary rocks of the Upper Senonian Mirkovo Formation (reddish limestones and marls), which are in turn overlain by flysch of the Chugovo Formation (Campanian-Maastrichtian in age) (Moev and Antonov, 1978). Based on their structures, host rocks, cross-cutting relationships and alterations on the surface of the products of the Chelopech volcanic complex, have been subdivided into 3 units:

(I) dome-like volcanic bodies – andesites and trachydacites,

(II) lava and agglomerate flows – of latitic-trachydacitic and dacitic composition,

(III) the Vozdol volcanic breccias and volcanics – basaltic-andesites, and andesites to latites (Stoykov et al., 2002; 2004).

Several dykes are exposed to the east of to the Chelopech volcanic complex (Fig. 2). They strike predominately in an east west direction and intrude into the Pre-upper Cretaceous metamorphic basement. They do not show cross-cutting relationships to the Chelopech volcanic complex. The largest dyke is more than 7 km in length. These dykes have andesitic, latitic, dacitic, and trachydacitic compositions. Their phenocrysts (> 40 volume %) consist of plagioclase, zoned amphibole, minor biotite, and titanite; whereas the microlites consist only of plagioclase and amphibole. These dykes host barite mineralisation in the region and the Kashana mine. The magmatic products in the areas of the Elatzite and Chelopech deposits reveal similar Sr, Nd, and Hf characteristics, where the tendency of an increase of 90 (Nd) and a decrease of 90 (Hf) zircon could be related to minor assimilation of host rocks within parts of the magmatic chamber (Stoykov et al. 2004).

The Kashana deposit is hydrothermal, vein type and was discovered in 1929 and its underground operation started in 1939. The deposit was mined by 8 operational underground levels. The main barite vein is 280 m long and from 0.2 to 10 m thick. The economic vein has a depth of more than 450 m.

Mining continued until 1971 when its operation was stopped. Numerous smaller barite veins in the area of the main one have been described. The mineralization is related to Upper Cretaceous altered Ca-alkaline intermediate small intrusive. Barite is the main mineral, minor minerals are presented by quartz, calcite, ankerite, fluorite, pyrite, galenite, sphalerite, chalcopryrite, etc. (Andreevich, et al. 1989).

	Quaternary
	Dioritic porphyrites
	Andesites and andesitic-dacites
	Sandstone formation
	Conglomerate formation
	Breccia-conglomerate formation
	Amphibole and amphibole-biotite granodiorites (vYδPz₂ – Vezhen pluton)
Berkovitsa Group	
	Diabases and Diabasic tuffs
	Low-crystalline schists and phyllites
	Arda Group (migmatized gneisses, gneiss-schists and amphibolites)

Fig. 2. Geological map of Bulgaria, Teteven sheet, 100 000 scale (after Cheshitev et al., 1995)

Barite content in the higher levels of the Kashana mine is from 48 to 93% (about 80% average) and it decreases in depth to 40%, while quartz content increases up to 50% and calcite up to 5% in the lowest mining level of 1150 m (Andreevich, et al. 1989).

Analytical techniques

To determine mineral composition of barite raw material, 3 color types of it were sampled: white, greenish colored – A, and pinkish colored – B (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Studied sample from the Kashana deposit: A - greenish coloured zone, B - pinkish coloured zone

Polished sections from the lower mined levels of the Kashana deposit were prepared for examination in reflected light. They were investigated under reflected light with a Leica DM2500P microscope at the University of Mining and Geology “St. Ivan Rilski”, Sofia, Bulgaria. The microphotographs illustrating the mineral composition were taken with a Leica DFC295 integrated digital camera, CMOS type sensor. The same also served to more precisely identify interesting mineral grains subject to microprobe analysis. The electron microprobe analyses were performed with a JEOL JSM-6010 PLUS LA X-ray spectral micro analyser, with an EDS spectrometer at the University of Mining and Geology “St. Ivan Rilski”, Sofia, Bulgaria. The mode of operation was determined by the following analytical conditions: 20 kV accelerating voltage. No standards were used. The measurements of one powdered sample of barite with greenish colored zone were performed on a Bruker D2-Phaser X-Ray powder diffractometer. The conditions which were applied during the measurements were the following: Cu radiation with wavelength $\lambda = 1,54184$, current - 10 mA, voltage - 30 kV, increment 0.02° in the interval of 2θ $7-90^\circ$ for 30 min of gathering diffraction data. The measurements were performed at the Laboratory of Powder Diffraction at the University of Mining and Geology “St. Ivan Rilski”.

Mineral composition

The optical microscope, X-Ray powder diffraction, and SEM investigation shows that the major mineral in the raw material is barite. Minor minerals are presented by quartz, calcite, and hematite.

The white raw material is composed mostly of barite and quartz. According to the X-Ray powder diffraction analyses, the greenish zone is composed of barite – 66%, muscovite – 28,5%, quartz – 5%, and hematite – below 1%. The colour of the pinkish zone is related to the hematite content.

Fig. 4. Hematite in barite and quartz

Fig. 5. X-Ray powder diffraction pattern of barite raw material

The barite raw material from the Kashana deposit is characterised by its high whiteness and low Sr content. The SEM investigation shows that Sr content is below 1.5%.

Fig. 6. A SEM image of analysed barites

Table 1. Chemical composition of studied barites in wt. %

Sample	Ba	Sr	S	O
001	67.42	1.13	14.15	17.30
002	62.91	1.26	14.44	21.39

Conclusion

The Kashana barite deposit is hydrothermal, vein type. Its formation is related to Late Cretaceous magmatic activity in the Elatzite-Chelopech ore field. The mineralisation is hosted in altered dykes of andesitic, latitic, dacitic, and trachydacitic compositions.

The combined optical microscope, SEM, and XRD investigation of samples from the lowest mining levels of Kashana barite mine suggest that:

- The main mineral in this part of the deposit is barite; minor ones are presented by muscovite, quartz, and hematite.
- The barite raw material is characterised by high whiteness and low Sr content.

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References

- Andreevich M., Bozhinov, K., Velinov, I., Grigorov, A., Zhelyazkova-Panayotova, M., Ivanov, I., Kanazirski, M., Katskov, N., Popov, S., Angelov, T. & Trashliev, S. (1989). *Non-metallic mineral deposits in Bulgaria. Vol. 2. Endogenic industrial minerals and rocks.* 260. Technika, Sofia. (in Bulgarian with English abstract).
- Cheshitev, G., Milanova, V., Sapunov, I., & Chumashenko, P. (1995). Geological map of Bulgaria on 100 000 scale, Teteven map sheet.
- Dabovski, C. (1988). Precambrian in the Srednogorie zone (Bulgaria). – In Cogne, J., D. Kozhoukharov. H. G. Krautner (Eds.). *Precambrian in Younger Fold Belts. Essex.* 841-847.
- Dabovski, C., Boyanov, I., Hrishev, H., Nikolov, T., Sapunov, I., Yanev, Y., & Zagorchev, I. (2002). Structure and Alpine evolution of Bulgaria. *Geol. Balcanica*, 32/2–4, 9–15.
- European Commission, Study on the EU's list of Critical Raw Materials (2020), Factsheets on Critical Raw Materials. (<http://www.europa.eu>).
- Haydoutov, I. (2001). The Balkan island-arc association in West Bulgaria. *Geol. Balcanica*, 31/1–2, 109–110.
- Kamenov, B., von Quadt, A., & Peytcheva, I. (2002). New insight into petrology, geochemistry, and dating of the Vezhen pluton, Bulgaria. *Geochem. Mineral. Petrol.*, 39, 3–25.
- Kamenov, B. K., Nedialkov, R., Yanev, Y., & Stoykov, S. (2003): Petrology of Late Cretaceous ore-magmatic centers from Central Srednogorie, Bulgaria. In: Bogdanov, K. and Strashimirov, S. (eds.): *Cretaceous porphyry-epithermal systems of the Srednogorie zone, Bulgaria. Society of Economic Geologists. Guidebook Series 36*, 133 pp.
- Moev, M. & Antonov, M. (1978). Stratigraphy of the Upper Cretaceous in the eastern part of Strelcha Chelopech line. *Ann. de l'École sup. mines et géol.*, 23, Fasc. II Géol., 7–27 (in Bulgarian with English abstract).
- Stoykov, S., Yanev, Y., Moritz R., & Fontignié, D. (2002). Late Cretaceous magmatism of the Chelopech region, the Central Srednogorie volcanic-intrusive zone (Bulgaria). - *Geol. Carpat. Special issue / 2002. 53 (electronic version)*.
- Stoykov, S. & Pavlishina, P. (2003). New data for Turonian age of the sedimentary and volcanic succession in the southeastern part of the Etropole Stara Planina Mountain, Bulgaria. *C. R. Acad. bulg. Sci.* 56/6, 55 60.
- Stoykov, S., Peytcheva, I., Von Quadt, A., Moritz, R., Frank M., & Fontignie, D. (2004). Timing and magma evolution of the Chelopech volcanic complex (Bulgaria). *Swiss Bulletin of Mineralogy and Petrology* 84 (1), 101-117.